

The Sound Morphing Toolbox: Musical Instrument Sound Modeling and Transformation Techniques

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Abstract. Sound morphing requires the use of several audio processing algorithms involving the analysis, transformation, and resynthesis of sounds. The aim of this demo is to review the techniques implemented in the sound morphing toolbox (SMT). The SMT is open-source and freely available on GitHub. This demo will cover the analysis, transformation, and resynthesis steps used in standard morphing techniques applied to isolated notes from musical instrument sounds, such as sinusoidal modeling, spectral envelope estimation, time-scale modification, and resynthesis models. The demo will include sound examples to illustrate each step and a hands-on session to show the participants how to use the SMT.

1 Motivation and Relevance

Perceptually, sound morphing is a transformation that gradually blurs the categorical distinction between the sounds being morphed by blending their sensory attributes [4]. When morphing musical instrument sounds, the challenge lies in interpolating across dimensions of timbre to produce the perception of hybrid musical instruments. Figure 1 shows a striking example of image morphing to illustrate sound morphing with a visual analogy. For musical instrument sounds, the corresponding transformation gradually transitions from the source instrument to the target instrument. Additionally, the midpoint ($\alpha = 0.5$) should give rise to the perception of a hybrid instrument that resembles both source and target instruments at the same time. To achieve that, we need a sound model that captures perceptual information and transformation strategies that allows manipulating this information in a perceptually meaningful way.

This demo will explore the methodological foundations and philosophical implications of morphing, from the conceptual formalization of morphing to the categorical perception of sounds. Morphing raises important issues in perception and cognition both in terms of research questions and the mathematical and computational means to address them. How is the morph represented in the brain given the representations of the source and target stimuli?

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Fig. 1. Image morphing used to illustrate the aim of sound morphing.

The topic of the proposed demo overlaps with several of the topics of interest of the CMMR community, such as audio and music processing; representations of sound and music; timbre and musical instruments; sound and music analysis, synthesis, and transformation; philosophical implications and methodological foundations; and expression and performative aspects of music. Sound morphing uses several audio and music processing algorithms for the analysis, synthesis, and transformation of sounds. For example, sinusoidal modeling, additive synthesis, spectral modeling, and time-scale modification. Given the strong connection between musical instruments and timbre [1], interesting morphing transformations happen across dimensions of timbre perception [4] and timbre features [2] lie at the core of sound morphing.

2 Innovation

Sound morphing has found creative, technical, and research applications in the literature. In music composition, sound morphing allows the exploration of the sonic continuum [22,10,15] by creating hybrid sounds that are intermediate between a source and a target sounds. Sound morphing is also used in audio processing, sound synthesis, and sound design [21,6]. Additionally, sound morphing techniques have been used to investigate different aspects of timbre perception [9,5,19]. More recently, Google Magenta's *NSynth* <https://magenta.tensorflow.org/nsynth-instrument> applied machine learning techniques to sound morphing. New technologies push the boundaries of what is possible to achieve in terms of sound transformations. Particularly, the great yet unexplored potential for creative applications in music composition and performance that sound morphing possesses is capable of driving further developments in creative music systems.

The primary aim of this demo is to introduce the Sound Morphing Toolbox (SMT) to the participants. The SMT contains MATLAB® implementations of sound modeling and transformation algorithms used to morph musical instrument sounds. The SMT is open-source and freely available on GitHub¹, making it highly flexible, controllable, and customizable by the user. This hands-on workshop is aimed mainly at less technically inclined participants such as composers or researchers without the technical background. During the workshop, participants will be guided on how to use the SMT

¹ <https://github.com/marcelo-caetano/sound-morphing>

step by step. Our aim is to provide an intuitive rather than technical understanding of the audio processing algorithms used. By the end of the workshop, the participants will be able to make informed decisions about audio processing algorithms and parameter values and use the SMT on their own. Additionally, the workshop will draft a research agenda for sound morphing that introduces technical aspects, aesthetic and perceptual issues. Finally, we will identify shortcomings of the currently available pieces of morphing software listed above and research opportunities.

3 Research

The SMT has open-source implementations of sound modeling and transformation algorithms based on the sinusoidal model [14,18] and the source-filter model [20,4]. The demo will review several classic audio processing algorithms widely used in sound analysis, transformation, and resynthesis, giving the participants a broad overview of musical instrument sound morphing and the tools to use them.

The demo will briefly review the analysis steps, namely parameter estimation, peak selection, partial tracking, partial selection, and harmonic selection in the SMT. In additive synthesis, the estimation of the parameters can use nearest-neighbor estimation [14] or parabolic interpolation under linear, log [18], or power scaling [3]. Peak selection [17] allows to only keep the parameters of the spectral peaks that correspond to sinusoids. Partial tracking [14] connects these peaks across frames to create time-varying sinusoids called *partials*, that are further selected according to their duration and harmonicity.

The demo will cover spectral envelope estimation with linear prediction [12] and iterative cepstral smoothing [16]. The demo will also cover the time-scaling modification (TSM) and frequency transposition techniques currently implemented in the SMT. TSM uses SOLA-FS [11]. Frequency transposition uses the sinusoids, with the frequencies transposed by intervals in cents. The amplitudes can be transposed or preserved using the spectral envelope [4]. Finally, the demo will cover both additive and source-filter resynthesis techniques. The SMT has implementations of additive synthesis by cubic-phase polynomial fitting [14], phase reconstruction by frequency integration [13], and overlap add [8,7]. Additionally, the residual from sinusoidal analysis is further modeled with the source-filter paradigm. The demo will briefly discuss residual modeling by time-varying linear prediction estimation [18].

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